

Contribution of gas kinetic theory to galaxy dynamics

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Abstract:

Basing steady-state galaxy dynamics on the Vlasov equation and integrating observational data, we opt for a velocity ellipsoid whose major axis points towards the center of the galaxy. The calculation then gives its evolution in space, as well as the velocity field with a solid body at the center of the galaxy, and a velocity that tends towards a plateau at the periphery. Considerations based on the shape of the velocity ellipsoid thus reveal the necessary presence of an invisible component driving the galaxy's entire dynamics - a dark matter halo in the Standard Model, or a halo or gap in a negative-mass environment in the Janus cosmological model.

1 – Choosing a form for the velocity distribution function:

We know that the dynamics of galaxies is dominated by their stellar component, which represents a non-collisional system that must satisfy the Vlasov equation. Calling up \vec{c}_o the macroscopic velocity and Ψ the gravitational potential, and restricting ourselves to stationary solutions, the equation becomes:

$$(1) \quad \vec{v} \cdot \nabla_r L_n f - \nabla_r \Psi \cdot \nabla_v L_n f = 0$$

We also know that this system of mass points cannot be treated as a simple self-gravitating system, and that a component of unknown nature makes a major contribution to the gravity field. All we can do is attempt to construct a solution to this Vlasov equation by placing our assumptions on the form of the velocity distribution function. We will first express equation (1) in terms of residual velocity $\vec{C} = \vec{v} - \vec{c}_o$ [3]. Bearing in mind that in stationary conditions, for reasons of symmetry:

$$(2) \quad \vec{c}_o \cdot \nabla_r L_n(f) = 0$$

this equation is written:

$$(3) \quad \vec{C} \cdot \nabla_r \ln(f) - \left(\nabla_r \Psi + \vec{c}_o \nabla_r \vec{c}_o \right) \cdot \nabla_C \ln(f) - \nabla_C \ln(f) \cdot \vec{C} : \nabla_r \vec{c}_o = 0$$

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The terms $\nabla_c L_n f \vec{C}$ and $\nabla_d \vec{c}_o$ are dyad matrices composed from two vectors. Let $a_i b_j$ and $c_i d_j$ be two dyad matrices. The expression in the equation is of the type :

$$(4) \quad ab:cd = \sum_{i,j} a_i b_j c_j d$$

In axisymmetry, the most general velocity ellipsoid has its principal axes oriented as follows.

Fig.1 = Velocity ellipsoid in axisymmetry.

In the diametral plane, one of the axes points towards the geometric center. We're now going to use the only data we have, which refer to the vicinity of the Sun. We know that two transverse axes are of comparable size, complemented by a third of double their length, approximately directed towards the galaxy's center. This deviation, known as vertex deviation, is classically considered to result from interaction with the nearby spiral arm, and we do not take it into account.

We know that the choice of a particular shape for the velocity ellipsoid determines both the spatial evolution of its axes and the rotation curve. So if we opt for a velocity spheroid:

$$(5) \quad L_n f^o = A_{(\rho,z)} + B_{(\rho,z)}(U^2 + V^2 + W^2)$$

his expression becomes:

$$(6) \quad L_n f^o = Cst + L_n n - \frac{mC^2}{2kT}$$

where T is a constant and where f^o becomes the Maxwell-Boltzmann function. The velocity field then corresponds to solid-state rotation.

$$(7) \quad \vec{c}_o = \omega_o \vec{k} \wedge \vec{r}$$

A medium with a Maxwellian distribution function is one dominated by collisions. Thermal conductivity and viscous dissipation proceed, from clean to close, by collisions. Such a medium, with this distribution function, is as if endowed with a thermal conductivity, if not infinite, at least very high, and is thus equipped with a constant absolute temperature T at

all its points. The high viscosity of the medium prevents the gaseous layers from sliding over each other (differential rotation). Hence solid-body rotation.

In the solution we're going to develop, we'll opt for the velocity ellipsoid configuration shown in the figure below.

Fig.2 : Ellipsoid of velocities.

Along these three directions P, Q, R , we can carry the quantities (the length of these three axes of the ellipsoid) :

$$\sigma_P = \langle C_P^2 \rangle$$

$$\sigma_Q = \langle C_Q^2 \rangle$$

$$\sigma_R = \langle C_R^2 \rangle$$

The logarithm of the function f is then an elliptical polynomial, a function of the components U, V, W of the thermal agitation velocity \vec{C} , also called residual velocity by astrophysicists.

We have :

(8)

$$\ln(f) = \ln(B) - \frac{m}{2kH} C^2 + a(C \cdot \mathbf{r})^2 + \alpha[\mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r})]^2$$

By introducing the form of the solution into this, we obtain a polynomial of order 3, with respect to the components U, V, W of the residual velocity. The third-order terms give :

(9)

$$-\frac{m}{2k} C^2 C \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{r}} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2a(C \cdot \mathbf{r}) \cdot C \cdot C + C \cdot \frac{\partial a}{\partial \mathbf{r}} (C \cdot \mathbf{r})^2 + C \cdot \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial \mathbf{r}} [\mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r})]^2 = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(10) \quad & -\frac{m}{2k} (C_x^2 + C_y^2 + C_z^2) \left(C_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + C_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + C_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) \right) \\
& + 2a (C_x^2 + C_y^2 + C_z^2) (xC_x + yC_y + zC_z) \\
& + \left(C_x \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} + C_y \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} + C_z \frac{\partial a}{\partial z} \right) (xC_x + yC_y + zC_z)^2 \\
& + \left(C_x \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} + C_y \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} + C_z \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial z} \right) (-yC_x + xC_y)^2 = 0
\end{aligned}$$

Which gives :

$$(11) \quad C_x^3 : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ax + x^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} + y^2 \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} = 0$$

$$(12) \quad C_y^3 : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ay + y^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} + x^2 \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} = 0$$

$$(13) \quad C_z^3 : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2az + z^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial z} = 0$$

$$(14) \quad C_x^2 C_y : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ay + x^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} + 2xy \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} + y^2 \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} - 2xy \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} = 0$$

$$(15) \quad C_y^2 C_x : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ax + y^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} + 2xy \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} + x^2 \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} - 2xy \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial y} = 0$$

$$(16) \quad C_x^2 C_z : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2az + x^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial z} + 2xz \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} + y^2 \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial z} = 0$$

$$(17) \quad C_y^2 C_z : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2az + y^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial z} + 2yz \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} + x^2 \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial z} = 0$$

$$(18) \quad C_z^2 C_x : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ax + z^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} + 2xz \frac{\partial a}{\partial z} = 0$$

$$(19) \quad C_z^2 C_y : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ay + z^2 \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} + 2yz \frac{\partial a}{\partial z} = 0$$

(20)

$$C_x C_y C_z : 2yz \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} + 2xz \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} + 2xy \frac{\partial a}{\partial z} - 2xy \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial z} = 0$$

Assuming that a and α depend on neither r , nor z , we get:

(21)

$$C_x^3 \equiv C_z^2 C_x \equiv C_y^2 C_x : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ax = 0$$

(22)

$$C_y^3 \equiv C_x^2 C_y \equiv C_z^2 C_y : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2ay = 0$$

(23)

$$C_z^3 \equiv C_x^2 C_z \equiv C_y^2 C_z : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + 2az = 0$$

In addition :

(24)

$$\rho^2 = x^2 + y^2 \implies \begin{cases} \frac{\partial \rho^2}{\partial x} = 2x \\ \frac{\partial \rho^2}{\partial y} = 2y \end{cases}$$

We get :

(25)

$$C_x^3 \equiv C_z^2 C_x \equiv C_y^2 C_x : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho^2} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + a = 0$$

(26)

$$C_y^3 \equiv C_x^2 C_y \equiv C_z^2 C_y : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho^2} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + a = 0$$

(27)

$$C_z^3 \equiv C_x^2 C_z \equiv C_y^2 C_z : -\frac{m}{2k} \frac{\partial}{\partial z^2} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) + a = 0$$

After integration :

(28)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho^2} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) = \frac{2k}{m} a \implies \frac{1}{H} = \frac{2k}{m} a \rho^2 + f_1(z^2)$$

(29)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z^2} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) = \frac{2k}{m} a \implies \frac{1}{H} = \frac{2k}{m} a z^2 + f_2(\rho^2)$$

The f_1 function depends only on z^2 . So, if we derive (28) with respect to z^2 , we can write

(30)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z^2} \left(\frac{2k}{m} a \rho^2 + f_1(z^2) \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial z^2} f_1(z^2) = \frac{\partial}{\partial z^2} \left(\frac{1}{H} \right) = \frac{2k}{m} a$$

Thus :

(31)

$$f_1(z^2) = \frac{2k}{m}az^2 + k_z$$

And :

(32)

$$\frac{1}{H} = \frac{2k}{m}a\rho^2 + \frac{2k}{m}az^2 + k_z$$

At the origin we have $\frac{1}{H} = k_z$ that we set equal to the constant $\frac{1}{H} = \frac{1}{T_0}$ which gives :

(33)

$$\frac{1}{H} = \frac{2k}{m}a\rho^2 + \frac{2k}{m}az^2 + k_z$$

Introducing the characteristic length r_0 gives

(34)

$$r_0^2 = \frac{m}{2akT_0} \implies H = \frac{T_0}{1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2}}$$

We will now decompose the residual velocity vector according to its projections on the axes < P, Q, R

(35)

$$C_r = C \cdot R = C \cdot \frac{\mathbf{r}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|} = \frac{C \cdot \mathbf{r}}{\|\mathbf{r}\|}$$

(36)

$$C_p = C \cdot P = C \cdot \frac{\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r}}{\|\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r}\|} = \frac{C \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r})}{\|\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r}\|}$$

(37)

$$C_q = C - C_r - C_p$$

(38)

$$\|\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r}\|^2 = (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r}) \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r}) = (\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{k})(\mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{r}) - (\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r})(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}) = r^2 - z^2 = \rho^2$$

(39)

$$\ln(f) = \ln(B) + a_r C_r^2 + a_p C_p^2 + a_q C_q^2$$

(40)

$$\ln(f) = \ln(B) + \frac{(a_r - a_q)}{r^2} (C \cdot \mathbf{r})^2 + \frac{(a_p - a_q)}{\rho^2} [C \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r})]^2 + a_q C^2$$

(41)

$$\ln(f) = \ln(B) + \frac{(a_r - a_q)}{r^2} (C \cdot \mathbf{r})^2 + \frac{(a_p - a_q)}{\rho^2} [C \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r})]^2 + a_q C^2$$

Through identification:

(42)

$$a_q = -\frac{m}{2kH}$$

(43)

$$a = \frac{(a_r - a_q)}{r^2} \Rightarrow a_r = -\frac{m}{2kH} + ar^2 \quad (44)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{(a_p - a_q)}{\rho^2} \Rightarrow a_p = -\frac{m}{2kH} + a\rho^2$$

Let :

(45)

$$\rho_0^2 = \frac{m}{2\alpha kT_0}$$

We get :

(46)

$$a_r = -\frac{m}{2kT_0}$$

(47)

$$a_p = -\frac{m}{2kT_0} \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} - \frac{\rho^2}{\rho_0^2} \right)$$

(48)

$$a_q = -\frac{m}{2kT_0} + \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} \right)$$

We can then express the velocity distribution function as a function of the coordinates (C_r, C_p, C_q) :

(49)

$$f = f_0 e \left(-\frac{m}{2kT_0} \left[C_r^2 + C_p^2 \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} - \frac{\rho^2}{\rho_0^2} \right) + C_q^2 \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} \right) \right] \right)$$

with :

(50)

$$f_0 = n \left(\frac{m}{2\pi kT_0} \right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} - \frac{\rho^2}{\rho_0^2} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

This gives us the axis of the velocity ellipsoid.

(51)

$$\sigma_r = \sqrt{\frac{2kT_0}{m}}$$

(52)

$$\sigma_p = \sqrt{\frac{2kT_0}{m} / \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} - \frac{\rho^2}{\rho_0^2} \right)}$$

(53)

$$\sigma_q = \sqrt{\frac{2kT_0}{m} / \left(1 + \frac{r^2}{r_0^2} \right)}$$

We can see that

$$(54) \quad \sigma_p < \sigma_q < \sigma_r$$

At the center of the system, the Maxwellian velocity distribution:

(55)

$$\sigma_p = \sigma_q = \sigma_r$$

The component σ_r is independent of r . If we want to take observational data into account, this gives $\sigma_p \approx \sigma_q$. In our solution, this means $\frac{1}{\rho_o^2} \ll \frac{1}{r_o^2}$. At distance, the transverse axes tend towards zero, $\alpha \ll a$, while the radial axis retains its value.

Fig.4 : Evolution of the axes of the velocity ellipsoid

2 - Construction of the rotation curve

It's now the identification of the second-order terms that will give us the rotation speed law. In the Vlasov equation, this corresponds to the term

(56)

$$\nabla_C \ln(f) \cdot C : \nabla_r c_o = \text{Tr}(\mathbf{AB}) = 0$$

with :

(57)

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{A} = \nabla_C \ln(f) C \\ \mathbf{B} = \nabla_r c_o \end{cases}$$

Let's calculate B. According to (14) :

(58)

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{c}_0}{\partial \mathbf{r}} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial c_{0x}}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial c_{0y}}{\partial x} & 0 \\ \frac{\partial c_{0x}}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial c_{0y}}{\partial y} & 0 \\ \frac{\partial c_{0x}}{\partial z} & \frac{\partial c_{0y}}{\partial z} & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} & x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + \omega & 0 \\ -y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} - \omega & x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} & 0 \\ -y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} & x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Let's calculate A :

(59)

$$\mathbf{A} = \nabla_{\mathbf{C}} \ln(f) \mathbf{C}$$

Then we get :

(60)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} &= -\frac{m}{kH} \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{C} + 2a(\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \cdot \mathbf{r} \cdot \mathbf{C} + 2\alpha[\mathbf{C} \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r})] \cdot (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{r}) \\ &= \mathbf{A}_1 + \mathbf{A}_2 + \mathbf{A}_3 \end{aligned}$$

(61)

$$\mathbf{A}_1 = -\frac{m}{kH} \begin{pmatrix} C_x^2 & C_x C_y & C_x C_z \\ C_y C_x & C_y^2 & C_y C_z \\ C_z C_x & C_z C_y & C_z^2 \end{pmatrix},$$

(62)

$$\mathbf{A}_2 = 2a(xC_x + yC_y + zC_z) \begin{pmatrix} xC_x & xC_y & xC_z \\ yC_x & yC_y & yC_z \\ zC_x & zC_y & zC_z \end{pmatrix},$$

(63)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}_3 &= 2\alpha \begin{pmatrix} y^2 C_x - xy C_y \\ -xy C_x + x^2 C_y \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} (C_x \ C_y \ C_z) \\ &= 2\alpha \begin{pmatrix} y^2 C_x C_x - xy C_y C_x & y^2 C_x C_y - xy C_y C_y & y^2 C_x C_z - xy C_y C_z \\ -xy C_x C_x + x^2 C_y C_x & -xy C_x C_y + x^2 C_y C_y & -xy C_x C_z + x^2 C_y C_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

Consider the following two matrices

(64)

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} A_{xx} & A_{xy} & A_{xz} \\ A_{yx} & A_{yy} & A_{yz} \\ A_{zx} & A_{zy} & A_{zz} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{et} \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{pmatrix} B_{xx} & B_{xy} & B_{xz} \\ B_{yx} & B_{yy} & B_{yz} \\ B_{zx} & B_{zy} & B_{zz} \end{pmatrix}$$

The trace of their matrix product is given by:

(65)

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{AB}) = A_{xx}B_{xx} + A_{xy}B_{yx} + A_{xz}B_{zx} + A_{yx}B_{xy} + A_{yy}B_{yy} + A_{yz}B_{zy}$$

Let's calculate each term:

(66)

$$\begin{aligned} A_{xx} &= -\frac{m}{kH} C_x^2 + 2a(x^2 C_x^2 + yx C_x C_y + zx C_x C_z) + 2\alpha(y^2 C_x^2 - xy C_y C_x) \\ &= C_x^2 \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ax^2 + 2\alpha y^2 \right) + C_x C_y 2(a - \alpha)xy + C_x C_z 2axz \end{aligned}$$

(67)

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{yy} &= -\frac{m}{kH}C_y^2 + 2a(xC_xyC_y + yC_yyC_y + zC_zyC_y) + 2\alpha(-xyC_xC_y + x^2C_yC_y) \\
&= C_y^2 \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ay^2 + 2\alpha x^2 \right) + C_xC_y2(a - \alpha)xy + C_yC_z2ayz
\end{aligned}
\tag{68}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{xy} &= -\frac{m}{kH}C_xC_y + 2a(xC_xxC_y + yC_yxC_y + zC_zxC_y) + 2\alpha(y^2C_xC_y - xyC_yC_y) \\
&= C_xC_y \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2\alpha x^2 + 2\alpha y^2 \right) + C_y^22(a - \alpha)xy + C_yC_z2axz
\end{aligned}
\tag{69}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{yx} &= -\frac{m}{kH}C_yC_x + 2a(xC_xyC_x + yC_yyC_x + zC_zyC_x) + 2\alpha(-xyC_xC_x + x^2C_yC_x) \\
&= C_x^22(a - \alpha)xy + C_xC_y \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ay^2 + 2\alpha x^2 \right) + C_xC_z2ayz
\end{aligned}
\tag{70}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{xz} &= -\frac{m}{kH}C_xC_z + 2a(xC_xxC_z + yC_yxC_z + zC_zxC_z) + 2\alpha(y^2C_xC_z - xyC_yC_z) \\
&= C_z^22axz + C_xC_z \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ax^2 + 2\alpha y^2 \right) + C_yC_z2(a - \alpha)xy
\end{aligned}
\tag{71}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{yz} &= -\frac{m}{kH}C_yC_z + 2a(xC_xyC_z + yC_yyC_z + zC_zyC_z) + 2\alpha(-xyC_xC_z + x^2C_yC_z) \\
&= C_z^22ayz + C_xC_z2(a - \alpha)xy + C_yC_z \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ay^2 + 2\alpha x^2 \right)
\end{aligned}
\tag{72}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{yz} &= -\frac{m}{kH}C_yC_z + 2a(xC_xyC_z + yC_yyC_z + zC_zyC_z) + 2\alpha(-xyC_xC_z + x^2C_yC_z) \\
&= C_z^22ayz + C_xC_z2(a - \alpha)xy + C_yC_z \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ay^2 + 2\alpha x^2 \right)
\end{aligned}
\tag{4.3.7}$$

The terms with C_x^2 come from $A_{xx} B_{xx}$ and $A_{yx} B_{xy}$

$$\left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ax^2 + 2\alpha y^2 \right) \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \right) + 2(a - \alpha)xy \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + \omega \right) = 0
\tag{73}$$

The terms with C_y^2 come from $A_{xy} B_{yx}$ and from $A_{yy} B_{yy}$

$$\left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ay^2 + 2\alpha x^2 \right) \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \right) + 2(a - \alpha)xy \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} - \omega \right) = 0
\tag{74}$$

The terms with C_z^2 come from $A_{xz} B_{zx}$ and from $A_{yz} B_{zy}$

(75)

$$2axz \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} \right) + 2ayz \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} \right) = 0$$

The terms with $C_x C_y$ come from $A_{xy} B_{yx}$, $A_{xx} B_{xx}$, $A_{yx} B_{xy}$, $A_{yy} B_{yy}$

(76)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ax^2 + 2\alpha y^2 \right) \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} - \omega \right) + 2(a - \alpha)xy \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \right) \\ & + \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ay^2 + 2\alpha x^2 \right) \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + \omega \right) + 2(a - \alpha)xy \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The terms with $C_x C_z$ come from and from $A_{xx} B_{zx}$, $A_{xx} B_{xx}$, $A_{yx} B_{xy}$, $A_{yz} B_{yz}$

(77)

$$\begin{aligned} & (2axz) \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \right) + \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ax^2 + 2\alpha y^2 \right) \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} \right) \\ & + (2axy) \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + \omega \right) + 2(a - \alpha)xy \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

The terms with $C_y C_z$ come from and from $A_{xy} B_{yx}$, $A_{xz} B_{zx}$, $A_{yy} B_{yy}$, $A_{yz} B_{yz}$

(78)

$$\begin{aligned} & (2axz) \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} - \omega \right) + 2(a - \alpha)xy \left(-y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} \right) \\ & + (2ayz) \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \right) + \left(-\frac{m}{kH} + 2ay^2 + 2\alpha x^2 \right) \left(x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial z} \right) = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Now let's exploit the fact that ω depends only on ρ^2 and z^2 . Thus, from (30) we obtain :

(79)

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho^2}{\partial x} = 2x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \rho^2}$$

(80)

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho^2}{\partial y} = 2y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \rho^2}$$

(81)

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \rho^2} \frac{\partial \rho^2}{\partial y} = 2y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial \rho^2}$$

The equation with C_x^2 becomes:

(82)

$$\frac{\partial \ln \omega}{\partial \rho^2} = -\frac{(a - \alpha)}{\left(\frac{m}{kH} - 2\alpha \rho^2 \right)}$$

Placing ourselves in the particular context where a and α are constant throughout space, we obtain:

(83)

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \ln \omega}{\partial \rho^2} &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{2(a - \alpha)}{\left(\frac{m}{kT_0} + 2(a - \alpha)\rho^2 + 2az^2\right)} \\ &= -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho^2} \left[\ln \left(\frac{m}{kT_0} + 2(a - \alpha)\rho^2 + 2az^2 \right) \right]\end{aligned}$$

Thus :

(84)

$$\omega = \frac{\omega_{\rho_0}(z^2)}{\sqrt{\frac{m}{kT_0} + 2(a - \alpha)\rho^2 + 2az^2}}$$

In the same way as above, the equation with $C_x C_z$ gives us :

(85)

$$\frac{\partial \ln \omega}{\partial z^2} = -\frac{a}{\left(\frac{m}{kH} - 2\alpha\rho^2\right)}$$

Assuming that a and α are constant throughout the space, we obtain :

(86)

$$\omega = \frac{\omega_{z_0}(\rho^2)}{\sqrt{\frac{m}{kT_0} + 2(a - \alpha)\rho^2 + 2az^2}}$$

This gives us the rotation speed at a point:

(87)

$$v = \rho \cdot \omega = \rho \cdot \frac{\omega_0}{\sqrt{\frac{m}{kT_0} + 2(a - \alpha)\rho^2 + 2az^2}}$$

In the $z = 0$ plan : galaxie :

(88)

$$v = \frac{\omega_0 \rho}{\sqrt{\frac{m}{kT_0} + 2(a - \alpha)\rho^2}}$$

Bearing in mind that $\alpha \ll a$

(89)

$$v \simeq \frac{\omega_0 \rho}{\sqrt{\frac{m}{kT_0} + 2a\rho^2}}$$

This gives us linear growth near the center of symmetry (solid-body rotation) and a constant velocity plateau at the perimeter.:

Fig.5 : Rotation curve.

So we can see that the simple fact of having given a particular orientation to the velocity ellipsoid has provided :

- The way its axes evolve in space.
- The local value of the solid-body rotational velocity at the galaxy's center,
- With a velocity plateau at the periphery.

It's very important to note that this solution doesn't refer to a system of self-gravitating mass points in their own gravitational field. It simply refers to the motion of a galaxy in a gravity field of a priori unknown source. But we can immediately construct this potential, in the gravitational plane, simply by expressing that the gravitational field balances the centrifugal force:

$$(90) \quad \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \rho} = \frac{\omega_o^2 \rho}{\frac{m}{kT_o} + 2a\rho^2} = \frac{kT_o \omega_o^2}{m} \frac{\rho}{1 + \frac{\rho^2}{r_o^2}}$$

$$(91) \quad \Psi = \frac{\omega_o^2}{2a} L_n \sqrt{1 + \rho^2} + \phi(z)$$

At distance $\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial \rho} \approx \frac{1}{\rho}$ thus $\Delta \Psi \approx \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2}$, which does not depend on ρ

Most of the potential is therefore created not by the contribution of the masses of the galaxy's stars, but by an external entity of unknown nature. To account for this rotational velocity field, we must assume that the galaxy's field is supplemented by that created by a vast halo of positive-mass dark matter ([5]-[13]) or, in the context of the Janus cosmological model ([18]-[23]), which is strictly equivalent, that this contribution is attributable to a gap in a negative-mass environment.

5 - By comparing observational data.

If we compare the rotation curve obtained, apart from very rare examples, the curves deduced from the observations are significantly different..

Fig.6 : Rotation curves.

With the exception of a few galaxies, such as NGC 128, the rotation curves near the origin rarely show an evolution consistent with the formula obtained.

Fig.7 : NGC 128 rotation curve.

If there's one rotation curve that deviates from the one we've obtained, it's that of our own galaxy, the Milky Way.:

Fig.8 : Milky way rotation curve.

The singular shape near the origin is the result of cannibalism. Large galaxies devour small ones, but both are non-colliding systems. The small galaxy falls into the potential well of the large one. Its star population is compressed. And, like the skater or dancer who brings her arms alongside her body, conservation of angular momentum causes the rotational speed of these stars to increase. While the stars of the galaxy-ogre have very low rotational speeds, near the geometric center, this contribution populates this region with fast-rotating stars, giving the curve this singular shape, which bears witness to the history of this system..

7 – Conclusion

We planned to describe galaxy dynamics using the Vlasov equation. The logarithm of the distribution-solution function was assimilated to a polynomial of degree 3, a function of the components of the residual velocity. Using data from observations in the vicinity of the Sun, we opted for an axisymmetric stationary solution, with a velocity ellipsoid whose major axis points towards the center of the galaxy. By developing our calculation further, we found that the distribution function was Maxwellian at the center of the galaxy, and that this major axis remained constant in space, while the transverse axes tended towards zero at the periphery. Calculating the velocity gave a solid-body rotation at the center of the galaxy, and a tendency towards a peripheral velocity plateau. Purely theoretical considerations, based on the shape of the residual velocity distribution function alone, show that the field that creates this velocity does not originate from the masses present in the galaxy, but from an entity of unknown nature. The standard interpretation invokes the presence of a halo of positive-mass dark matter. Putting this in the context of the Janus model, an identical result is obtained with a gap in a uniform distribution of negative mass surrounding the galaxy, the density profile being merely the negative image of the dark matter halo. In presenting the data concerning

the velocity curves, we recall that these retain the trace of the successive cannibalization(s), the extra velocity being linked to the conservation of the angular momentum of the ingested galaxy which, like the one absorbing it, constitutes a non-collisional system, so that the angular velocities of the two cannot be adjusted..

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